

Possibility of Oscillating Electrical Field across the Membranes of the Organelles like Mitochondria – A Consequence of Mitchell's Chemi-osmotic Coupling

R. C. SRIVASTAVA*

Department of Chemistry, Birla Institute of Technology and Science, Pilani-333 031

Mitchell's chemi-osmotic hypothesis has been examined to reveal the possibility of the existence of oscillating electric field across the membranes of the organelles like mitochondria.

MITCHELL'S chemi-osmotic hypothesis¹ for oxidative and photosynthetic phosphorylation, broadly speaking, envisages a cyclic operation. In the first part of the cycle, on one side of the biological membrane (say side 1) either by the action of light or by respiration, occurs a proton generating oxidation process, and on the other side of the membrane (say side 2) occurs the hydrolysis of adenosine triphosphate (ATP) which is a proton consuming process. Thus a proton concentration difference is established across the membrane. When this concentration difference becomes critical, the second part of the cycle begins. In this part of the cycle the adenosine triphosphatase (ATPase) activity is reversed, i.e. on the side 2 now commences the synthesis of AIP—a proton generating process, and on the side 1—a proton consuming reduction reaction. Since the energy derived from ATP hydrolysis is continuously required for metabolic activity of the cell, concentration of ATP within the cell should remain at a steady level, i.e. the amount of ATP lost by hydrolysis should be replenished by its synthesis. It is easy to see that the electrical potential difference developed across the membrane in the first part of the cycle wherein ATP is hydrolysed should be equal in magnitude but opposite in sign to that developed in the second part of the cycle in which ATP is synthesised. It is also easy to visualise that frequency of this cycle should be very high so that ATP level in the living cell remains steady. In fact the frequency should be determined by the metabolic activity of the cell—more the ATP dependent metabolic activity higher should be the frequency. If it is the same enzyme which brings about both synthesis and hydrolysis of ATP it would appear that the ATPase enzyme should have at least two conformations, one responsible for the hydrolysis and the other for the synthesis of AIP, possessing energies close to each other. Possibility of the existence of the two conformational states of this bifunctional ATPase enzyme is enough indicated in literature²⁻⁵.

Thus it appears on a priori grounds that this kind of high frequency electrical oscillations should exist across the membranes of all ATP synthesising

organelles/organisms, e.g. mitochondria, chloroplasts and the organisms like *Halobacterium halobium* to which the Mitchell's mechanism is applicable. Existence of such oscillating electrical fields which should form a very strong evidence in favour of Mitchell's chemi-osmotic hypothesis has so far not been explicitly demonstrated even across the membranes of mitochondria. But nevertheless several circumstantial evidences indicating the existence of oscillating electric fields generated by biological materials (living membranes/cells) are documented in literature.

Frohlich^{6,7} predicted that chemical energy of living cells could evoke high frequency electrical oscillations. Indirect evidences in favour of Frohlich's predictions have gradually accumulated⁸⁻¹². Studies in the Raman and microwave range^{7,13}, microdielectrophoresis of dividing cells^{14,15} and cellular spin resonance^{16,17} contain some of the strong evidences. It has also been shown that the oscillating electrical fields are a property of the living cells and not of dead cells^{18,19}. Metabolic inhibitors suppressing the ATPase activity have been shown to repress the electrical field in living cells and frequency of the oscillating field is maximal at or near mitosis^{16,20}.

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*Present address: Department of Chemistry, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221 005.

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